

Local Government in Austria

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

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November 2021

The Country Report on Local Government in Austria is a product of the LoGov-project: “Local Government and the Changing Urban-Rural Interplay”.

The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 823961.

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1. The System of Local Government in Austria

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Types of Local Governments

The Austrian Constitution defines Austria as a federal state formed by nine *Länder*. These are further divided into districts (*Bezirke*), administrative units executing tasks for both the *Länder* and the national government, where no statutory city exists. There are, however, 15 statutory cities (*Statutarstädte*) with a special statute, combining the authority and responsibilities of a municipality and a district. Municipalities (*Gemeinden*) are granted the right to self-government as independent administrative bodies in their sphere of competence by Article 116 of the Austrian Constitution. In sum, the three relevant levels of government are the central government, *Länder* and municipal level with some exceptions such as statutory cities which are assigned responsibilities from district level as well as the Capital City of Vienna, which is a municipality and a *Land* at the same time.

Legal Status of Local Governments

The Austrian Constitution of 1920 entrenches and protects municipalities not only as local administrative units but also as institutions of self-government (Article 116(1)). However, Articles 115–20 of the Constitution also extensively predetermine the organization of municipalities, their powers and intergovernmental relations. This tight national constitutional regime reduces the complementary power of the *Länder* under Article 115(2) of the Constitution to autonomously regulate local government through their own laws (*Gemeindeordnungen*) which results in a tendency towards uniformity.

As for their responsibilities, municipalities may only act lawfully on the basis of competences that are expressly conferred upon them and circumscribed by either national or *Land* legislation. However, this legislation *must* make them responsible for ‘all matters that exclusively or preponderantly concern the local community’ and are ‘suited to performance by the community within its local boundaries’ (Article 118(2) of the Austrian Constitution). Whether national and *Land* legislators observe this rule is checked by the Constitutional Court.

The own autonomous competences of municipalities on this basis, which exist in addition to the competences delegated from the national or *Land* government, include, in particular, the following areas: traffic and transport; gas, water and electricity supply; waste collection; sewage disposal; kindergarten, parts of education; elderly care; cemeteries; and cultural and

sport facilities are all within the competences of municipal administration. For providing these public services, municipalities manage their own budget independently and can own assets of all kind and operate economic enterprises. A major share of municipal budgets comes from intragovernmental transfers, which is a complex system of re-distribution of revenues across all levels of government.

(A)Symmetry of the Local Government System

The distribution of powers is uniform for all municipalities and therefore fails to take into account differences between bigger urban and smaller rural local governments. The Austrian Constitution adheres to the ‘principle of the abstract uniform municipality’, as enshrined already in 1920. This means that, with the exceptions of the above-mentioned statutory cities and the capital Vienna,¹ all municipalities enjoy, also regarding their competences, equal legal status irrespective of variations in territorial size, population or economic and administrative capacities.

Performing the same tasks as big municipalities can be challenging for Austria’s smaller municipalities. The latter are the majority, as 55 per cent of 2,096 municipalities (in 2018) have less than 2,000 inhabitants and 88 per cent have less than 5,000 residents. Thus, Article 116(a) of the Austrian Constitution lays down the possibility for inter-municipal cooperation in the form of local authority associations (*Gemeindeverband*) to manage certain areas of responsibility such as water supply or waste management (single-purpose associations). Since 2011, the founding of multi-purpose associations (*Mehrzweckverband*) between municipalities is possible in order to go beyond coordination and centralize public service provision such as regional planning, economic development or welfare services. Even though it is legally possible, such multi-purpose associations are not very common.

Another form of cooperation is the possibility of municipalities merging into an institutionalized regional authority, the ‘territorial municipality’ (*Gebietsgemeinde*), as foreseen by Article 120 of the Constitution. The territorial municipality offers the possibility of bundling and/or controlling as many tasks as possible on a regional level, while at the same time maintaining decentralized provision of services by the individual local communities. The preservation of the local identity is guaranteed by own local mayors and municipal councils. However, this form of territorial merger (as opposed to amalgamations) is considered ‘dead law’, as it has never been put into practice.²

¹ Vienna has different competences because it is at the same time a municipality and one of the nine *Länder* (Arts 108-112 of the Constitution).

² Thomas Prorok and others, ‘Struktur, Steuerung und Finanzierung von kommunalen Aufgaben in Stadtregionen’ (KDZ 2013) <<https://www.kdz.eu/de/content/struktur-steuerung-und-finanzierung-von-kommunalen-aufgaben-stadtregionen>> accessed 31 January 2020.

Political and Social Context in Austria

The two major parties, the conservative Austrian People's Party and the Social Democratic Party of Austria have historically shared the parliamentary majority, with the right-wing Austrian Freedom Party ranging on third place with a significant share of votes since the 1990s. Other smaller parties are the Green Party and the liberal NEOS party. All mentioned parties are currently represented in different levels of government with different majorities. On the local level, apart from local independent candidate lists, the majority of municipalities are still split between the People's Party and the Social Democrats. This is also reflected in the organization of municipal associations, one being the Austrian Association of Municipalities (*Gemeindebund*), which is typically associated with the conservative party and smaller rural municipalities, and the Austrian Association of Cities and Towns (*Städtebund*), being organizationally closer to the Social Democrats and representative of larger cities.³ However, this differentiation should be seen in a more historical context, as many municipalities and cities are members of both associations.

As of 2018, 52 per cent of Austria's population lived in municipalities with less than 10,000 inhabitants and 48 per cent in only 86 larger towns and cities, with Vienna alone having 21 per cent of the Austrian population.

As in many countries, urban and rural areas in Austria face different social problems and demographic challenges. Regarding poverty and social exclusion, for example, residents of Austria's urban areas are more at risk than their rural counterparts because of more single parents' households and more households with no or little income.⁴ On the other hand, rural areas are confronted with out-migration especially of young people, women and highly educated people to cities. This has significant long-term effects on economic development, as well as the provision of health care and elderly care services.⁵

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

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Austrian Federal Constitution (B-VG, *Bundes-Verfassungsgesetz*), BGBl. No 1/1930 (WV) idF BGBl. I no 194/1999 (DFB)

³ The representation through either one of these associations is constitutionally regulated in Art 115(3) of the Constitution.

⁴ Österreichischer Städtebund, 'Österreichs Städte in Zahlen' (2017) 42.

⁵ Bundesministerium für Land- und Forstwirtschaft, Nachhaltigkeit und Wasserwirtschaft, 'Masterplan ländlicher Raum' (BMLFUW 2017).

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This project has received funding from
the European Union's Horizon 2020 re-
search and innovation programme under
grant agreement No 823961.

